

A2

A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

Case Studies Examination

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A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

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Abstract

The definition of the critical citation elements of cultural heritage objects (CHOs) informs one of the milestones of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects*. It is based on data gathered through the examination of case studies focusing on CHO citation models in plural – native and non-native – contexts, the replicability of CHO citation as well as cross-disciplinary exploratory interviews, along with the identification of the critical citation elements within the CHO metadata schemas. This deliverable aims to illustrate the results achieved in terms of the distinctive features, criticalities, habits, and shortcomings in citation practices related to cultural heritage objects and data.

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CHO	Cultural Heritage Object
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
PID	Persistent Identifier
PIDINST	Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Scientific Instruments
RDA	Research Data Alliance
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WG	Working Group

1. Introduction

This first part of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects* involved two main steps: the analysis of data representation models of cultural heritage objects (CHOs) through a literature review, and the analysis of three types of case studies aimed at capturing the citation relevance of cultural heritage objects and data from a cross-disciplinary perspective. Namely:

A2.1 / Cross-disciplinary exploratory interviews. Ten semi-structured interviews were conducted, based on a canvas of questions but open to the free sharing of ideas, experiences and stimuli.

A2.2 / Examination of case studies of CHO citation models: a quantitative analysis on citation practices of data repositories was carried out based on public data available in repository registries.

A2.3 / Examination of case studies on the replicability of CHO citations with the aim of identifying experiences related to the attribution of identifiers or citation standards to cultural heritage objects.

Starting from the definition of the rationale and the methodology applied for each section, this deliverable aims to illustrate the results achieved in terms of the distinctive features, criticalities, habits, and shortcomings in citation practices related to cultural heritage objects and data.

2 Cross-disciplinary exploratory interviews

This section of the deliverable provides a critical conceptual summary of the themes that emerged in the context of the exploratory interviews.

2.1 Rationale

The idea behind the interviews was to collect, understand and analyse the problem of citing cultural heritage objects from the point of view of those who use, consume and sometimes produce these objects in the course of their research.

The questions we particularly wanted to focus on are: what is meant by digital cultural object or more generally by cultural heritage object; what reference models are known, used or encountered in the representation of cultural heritage objects; what sources are actively used for the retrieval of cultural objects.

On the basis of these data, therefore, we wanted to highlight and analyse the specific experiences of researchers on the citation of such objects, in order to understand what kind of problems, if any, they encountered and what shortcomings they found in the citations they encountered or in the citation model possibly proposed by the sources of the objects, in order to elicit what, from their point of view, could be considered as critical citation elements, always bearing in mind the complexity and multidisciplinary nature inherent in each and every cultural object.

2.2 Methodology

The selection of interviewees focused in particular on the research community of the University of Padua, but also on researchers from museum areas and representatives of European Cultural Heritage projects. The people reached by the interviews deal with different research fields, all related to cultural heritage with an inter- and cross-disciplinary perspective.

The main scientific domains intercepted so far are: Arts and Architecture (with a focus on an interdisciplinary project between Medieval art and Chemistry), Archaeology, Geology (closely linked to Archaeology but also to Architecture), Chemistry, History of Science (see Fig. 1).

The research domains of the interviewees do not exhaustively cover the multidisciplinary inherent in cultural objects, but nevertheless represent a significant selection, both in terms of differentiation of research domains and from the point of view of cross-disciplinary intersections.

Fig. 1. Cultural objects cross-disciplinarity: interviewees' research domains.

From a practical point of view, the interviews, introduced by an invitation letter provided the background, aims, and objectives of the project, were conducted in-person or virtually, via Zoom platform.

The methodology followed for the interviews adhered to the principles of the qualitative research borrowed from grounded theory to allow for a narrative elicitation of the themes explored with the interviewees: starting from a canvas with 12 questions, an attempt was made to encourage the free sharing of ideas, experiences and stimuli, as far as possible.

To date, ten interviews were conducted but the richness of the insights from the interviews prompted a change in the initial planning, transforming the interviews into open conversations, broadening the target group of interviewees with the intention of convening a public panel before the end of the project. Also, the interview setting offered a valuable opportunity to introduce RDA and EOSC to the local research community, highlighting how their knowledge cannot be taken for granted.

Questions in the canvas:

1. *Presentation of interviewee (what are his/her main research interests and lines of research; his/her participation in research projects involving the production of digital objects)*

2. *From your point of view and research perspective, what do you mean by cultural object? and by digital object?*
3. *In conducting your research, where and how have you used digital objects? What kind of objects?*
4. *What are your digital objects sources?*
5. *If you have used digital objects, have you ever had to cite them? When citing them, which problems did you experience?*
6. *How do you cite them?*
7. *Have you ever had to cite or seen the same digital object cited in different disciplinary contexts? If yes, how? In what way?*
8. *What critical issues, if any, have you encountered/detected in the representation of the digital (cultural) object?*
9. *In particular, is provenance adequately represented? How much weight do you give to the identification/traceability of provenance?*
10. *What about the format specifications of the digital (cultural) object type mentioned?*
11. *In the use or creation of digital (cultural) objects, which representation models (e.g. ontologies) have you found?*
12. *Which elements should never be missing in the citation of a digital (cultural) object?*

2.3 Findings and Discussion

The immediate feedback received from the interviewees was very positive: the topics discussed aroused great interest and a desire to share and exchange ideas and points of view, and the issue of the citation of cultural objects emerged as very heartfelt, stimulating and fundamental. In fact, all the meetings held lasted much longer than the time initially planned (30 minutes).

The collection and analysis of the answers made it possible to extract some considerations that turned out to be very significant in the context of the project.

From your point of view and research perspective, what do you mean by cultural object?

The answers to this question confirmed the complex, multifaceted and inherently cross-disciplinary nature of cultural objects.

Indeed, the common perception of the researchers is that the very boundaries of the idea of a cultural object have become much wider over time, that there is something intangible and difficult

to define that turns an object into a cultural object, that the same object may be of cultural interest to some but not to others.

The concrete examples of cultural objects cited during the interviews also confirm this complexity: among the cultural objects cited we have, among others, the soil (archaeology), the human body (performance art), places (history of science).

Which problems did you experience in cultural objects citation?

Again, the answers to this question were consistently significant: all respondents had some difficulty when it came to citing cultural objects in their work, which once again confirms the importance and value of the project research topic.

The most frequently cited problematic aspects seem to be related to the lack of information in the data source: the metadata of cultural objects are sometimes incomplete or lacking information considered essential: in many digital archives permanent identifiers are missing, and there is often no indication of how to cite objects.

Additionally, the substantial lack of citation standards or even of citation practices recognised by the relevant disciplinary community means that each researcher frequently has to create the citation him/herself.

This leads to dissimilarity, inconsistency and can cause concerns with publishers who, in addition to not giving guidance on how to cite cultural objects themselves, place limits on the number of keystrokes for each contribution, making it disadvantageous for the author himself to insert long citations complete with links, which take away space from the actual content of the contribution.

Fig. 2. Problems for CHO citations.

Which elements should never be missing in the citation of a digital (cultural) object?

In defining a possible citation model for cultural objects, it is essential to identify which elements are indispensable for an effective citation that is as complete as possible but at the same time consistently concise.

In this case too, it was interesting and important to gather the views of researchers. The elements that emerged during the conversations as fundamental in citation were: URL, Location, Place of preservation, Author/Creator, Title, Date, Inventory number, Provenance, Year of update, Rights of re-use.

Whatever form the cultural object takes (physical object, its digital manifestation, native digital object), the aspect considered most relevant by almost all respondents is the possibility to locate the cultural object itself: elements such as the URL (for digital objects) or the storage venue and location (for physical objects) seems to be indispensable for a proper citation. In fact, the direct relationship with the cultural object allows the reader to have a first-hand experience of what is being said, providing him or her with the critical context to better understand the text, but also to confirm (or refute) the thesis expressed by the author.

In this regard, an important consideration must be made: the interviewees used the terms 'URL' or 'link', but for this to be really effective and useful in a citation it is necessary to use a persistent identifier (for example a DOI or an ARK PID) globally assigned to cultural objects.

3 Digital repositories data citation practices

This section of the deliverable focuses on a quantitative analysis of data repositories citation practices in order to determine whether data repositories advise their users about data citation.

3.1 Rationale

Investigate the citation practices of data repositories based on public data available in repository registries, with the aim to find out if data repositories, indexed in repository registries, provide guidelines to cite the data deposited in the repositories.

3.2 Methodology

A repositories registry is a searchable database that indexes metadata records describing data repositories. The most used repository registries are re3data.org¹, FAIRsharing.org², and OpenDOAR³. We found re3data.org repositories registry the most suitable for the purpose of the analysis as re3data.org Metadata Schema v2.2 (Vierkant 2014)⁴ contains the "Citation Guideline URL" metadata element. The metadata field is described in the schema as "The URL outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository".

We conducted a quantitative analysis of the re3data.org repositories registry data. Metadata records were retrieved via re3data.org API. It has to be noted that re3data.org API retrieves version 2.2 of the re3data.org metadata schema, whereas the user interface of the website uses the schema version 3.1. The "Citation Guideline URL" metadata element is part of both versions of the schema with the same description.

We focused the analysis of the repository records on the broad "Humanities and Social Sciences" subject area as we expected to find most of the cultural heritage digital repositories within this subject area. It wouldn't be possible to limit the query to the "Humanities" subject area as a repository record can be tagged with the "Humanities and Social Sciences" subject but not include the "Humanities" subject.

We cleaned and refined the retrieved metadata records using the OpenRefine tool⁵.

We also mapped the metadata standards provided in the re3data.org records to the URI of the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog⁶ metadata standards to find which metadata standards the repositories declare to use already exist in the Catalog.

¹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

² <https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Database>

³ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

⁴ Vierkant, P., Spier, S., Ruecknagel, J., Pampel, H., Fritze, F., Gundlach, J., Fichtmüller, D., Kindling, M., Kirchhoff, A., Göbelbecker, H.-J., Klump, J., Kloska, G., Reuter, E., Semrau, A., Schnepf, E., Skarupianski, M., Bertelmann, R., Schirmbacher, P., Scholze, F., Kramer, C., Witt, M., Fuchs, C., Ulrich, R., 2014. Schema for the description of research data repositories (2.2). DOI: 10.2312/re3.006

⁵ <https://openrefine.org/>

⁶ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

3.3 Findings and Discussion

As of 23 February 2023, 1144 re3data.org records exist in the "Humanities and Social Sciences" subject area, and the "Citation Guideline URL" metadata field is filled in in 542 (47.4 %) metadata records. A non-negligible part of the records (7.2 %) links to the same web page "Dataverse Best Practice on Data Citation" (Figure 3), so the data citation guidelines provided might also depend on the digital library platform on which the data repository is built upon.

SSH Repositories - Citation Guideline URL

Data retrieved: 23 February 2023

Fig. 3. Citation Guideline URL in SSH re3data.org records.

If we broaden the analysis to all metadata records on re3data.org, as of 6 March 2023 we found that about 53 % of the repository records filled in the "Citation Guideline URL" field (Figure 4).

All re3data Repositories - Citation Guideline URL

Data retrieved: 6 March 2023

Fig. 4. Citation Guideline URL in all re3data.org records.

As stated in the FORCE11 Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles, “A data citation should include a persistent method for identification that is machine actionable, globally unique, and widely used by a community”⁷. The re3data.org metadata schema provides the ‘PID system’ field to mark the persistent identifiers used by the data repository.

A further analysis of the metadata records from the subject area of Social Sciences and Humanities that filled in the Citation Guideline URL metadata element showed that the most frequently used PID systems are DOI⁸, Handle⁹, or both. Notably, around one-third of the records don’t provide any persistent identifiers (Figure 5).

⁷ <https://force11.org/info/joint-declaration-of-data-citation-principles-final>

⁸ <https://www.doi.org/>

⁹ <https://handle.net/>

SSH Repositories - PID System where Citation URL is not empty

Data retrieved: 23 February 2023

Fig. 5. PID systems in SSH re3data.org records that have non-empty Citation Guideline URL metadata field.

The quantitative analysis of data from repository registries leads to the finding that registries provide little information on how to cite data. Moreover, they do not state whether registered repositories endorse recommendations or guidelines for citing data, such as the recommendations of the RDA Data Citation Working Group¹⁰ or the FORCE11 Data Citation Principles.

The analysis of Social Sciences and Humanities repositories might suggest a modest level of awareness of the data citation topic. Further investigations of data citation practices of data repositories will be conducted on a subset of European repositories selected as case studies in the project.

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-citation-wg.html>

4 CHO citation replicability case study

The aim of this section is to illustrate, through the examination of specific case studies, the relevance of the adoption of persistent identifiers in the cultural heritage sector at any level (e.g., collection objects, environments, specimens, items, instruments), also with reference to the intention of creating meaningful metrics for data that respond to the diversity of data citation sources, thus including CHO citations.

4.1 Rationale

Identify and discuss specifically selected case studies with the aim of highlighting experiences related to the attribution of identifiers or citation standards to cultural heritage objects.

4.2 Methodology

The standardized citation of a cultural heritage object (CHO) implies the possibility that it can be identified, located, contextualized, enriched and counted.

The accountability of a citation, the accuracy in identifying the represented object, the possibilities of cross-disciplinary reuse or the positioning in a knowledge graph are potential uses related to the permanent identification of the object and its associated metadata.

The technological infrastructures, to count the future-proof standardized citation of a CHO, can be the same as those already in place for indexing and accounting academic Works, Datasets, or Patents.

The analysis of the case studies aims at identifying experiences related to the attribution of identifiers or citation standards to cultural heritage objects.

4.3 Heritage PIDs Project Case Studies

The Heritage PIDs project¹¹ has been identified as a source of case studies, analysis and practices. It is a Towards a National Collection Foundation project that “aims to offer guidance to cultural heritage organisations, those creating citation guidance and researchers on citing items in cultural heritage organisations”¹².

¹¹ <https://tanc-ahrc.github.io/HeritagePIDs>. See also other European Heritage PIDs initiatives currently underway with Europeana as a key player, as for example the national project PID Network Germany <https://www.pid-network.de>, which devotes a specific use case to the persistent identifiers addressing of cultural objects, holdings, and collections and their contexts (<https://www.pid-network.de/en/pid-sections/cultural-objects>) as well as the Belgian project LOD-ISNI <https://www.kbr.be/en/projects/lod-isni/project>.

¹² <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk>

Relevant Case Studies were identified from Heritage PIDs Resources¹³:

- Persistent Identifiers at the British Library (Madden 2020a)¹⁴
- Persistent Identifiers at the National Gallery (Madden 2020b)¹⁵
- Persistent Identifiers at the Natural History Museum (Madden 2021a)¹⁶
- Persistent Identifiers at Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh (Madden 2021b)¹⁷

4.3.1 Heritage PIDs Case Studies in brief

- 1) “The British Library implemented ARKs to address an internal use case and so the external aspect was not implemented due to resource constraints. The British Library adopted two types of identifier for content, to address different use cases and classes of material. DOIs were considered instead of ARKs but were discounted due to the central control the registration agencies have for DOIs. Working cooperatively with other organisations can result in wider benefits and adoption of identifiers. This comes with the burden of the additional time required to manage the increased number of dependencies”. (From: Madden 2020a).
- 2) “The National Gallery has been experimenting with various aspects of PIDs, through the Heritage PIDs’ experimental projects, the Gallery developed detailed requirements, including the need for a simple identifier registry for all available data and an open API with resolvable URIs. The resolvable URIs can then be used to map data against standard ontology systems, such as CIDOC-CRM to organize data and the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) to present images”. (From: Madden 2020b)
- 3) “Within natural history (*as in the Natural History Museum, London*) the scientific use of collections may be higher than the use of other cultural heritage collection items. Therefore the increase in open publishing practices and open data, seen in scientific publishing may drive change in management of natural history collections faster than other types of collections”. (From: Madden 2021a)
- 4) “One of the key takeaways from the *Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh* use of identifiers is the value in a simple approach, which could be adopted by other GLAM organisations. In part

¹³ <https://tanc-ahrc.github.io/HeritagePIDs/resources.html>

¹⁴ Madden, F., Kotarski, R., 2020. Persistent Identifiers at the British Library. DOI: 10.23636/1242

¹⁵ Madden, F., Kotarski, R., 2020. Persistent Identifiers at the National Gallery. DOI: 10.23636/1243

¹⁶ Madden, F., Woodburn, M., 2021. Persistent Identifiers at the Natural History Museum. DOI: 10.22020/kg9s-we61

¹⁷ Madden, F., Mitchell, L., 2021. Persistent Identifiers at Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh. DOI: 10.23636/pvfs-n308

this was deliberate but the lack of a historical accession register for the Herbarium probably made the decision easier at the time.(...) implementation of CETAF Stable Identifiers has also highlighted the importance of clarity around what exact item is being identified, which is often lacking in some implementations or users' interpretation of them. There is a lack of consensus across the sector around what an identifier should refer to, especially as regards a physical item versus a digital representation". (From: Madden 2021b)

The project has therefore led to conclusions regarding CHO compliant PIDs, dividing them primarily into three categories:

- [Human readable PIDs](#)
- [Machine readable PIDs](#)
- [Globally resolvable PIDs](#)

Common characteristics of the above-mentioned PIDs are that:

- collection items are persistently citable
- can be used internally across systems

The PIDs that belong to all three categories, and that appear to be eligible for a wide and effective use of the identifier in metadata, are as follows:

- [Digital Object Identifier](#) (DOI)
- [Archival Resource Key](#) (ARK)
- [International Standard Name Identifier](#) (ISNI)

4.4 PIDINST analogy

Given the importance of CHOs and associated metadata to the assessment of citation accountability and cross-cultural metadata enrichment and reuse, globally unique, persistent and resolvable identification of CHOs is crucial. Therefore, we have found a strong analogy between permanent identification of CHOs and the assignment of PIDs to research instruments. To introduce the nature of the aforementioned analogy, it is necessary to clarify that a description of a facility or research instrument may have several common characteristics with cultural heritage objects.

In thinking about equipment, it is easy to focus only on mass-produced objects (although seriality is something possible even for CHOs), but a significant part of the structures is something unique, sometimes made up of different elements, also produced in series, in other cases the instruments are built as unique pieces. As far as the instrumentation is concerned, the metadata and the need to identify and describe them are the same as those of the CHOs: locate them, describe them, identify them with respect to an ontology, identify them for a need to measure their impact, for research

integrity, identify them from a multidisciplinary or cross-disciplinary perspective of research. Even research infrastructures can be analogue or digital, tangible and intangible. Finally, among the CHOs it is possible that there are facilities or instrumentation, both of past and contemporary ages.

The Research Data Alliance Working Group Persistent Identification of Instruments (PIDINST) developed a community-driven solution for persistent identification of instruments which is discussed in (Stocker 2020)¹⁸ and (Krahl 2022)¹⁹.

4.5 Recommended CHO resolvable IDs

In the last version of the PIDINST schema all properties are either mandatory or recommended:

ID	property	obligation
1	Identifier	M
2	SchemaVersion	M
3	LandingPage	M
4	Name	M
5	Owner	M
6	Manufacturer	M
7	Model	R
8	Description	R
9	InstrumentType	R
10	MeasuredVariable	R
11	Date	R
12	RelatedIdentifier	R
13	AlternateIdentifier	R

From: "Table 1: Overview of PIDINST properties" (Krahl 2022)²⁰

Where metadata about ID property "should be used to link other resources of any kind related to the instrument, referring to a persistent identifier of this resource. (...). The allowed values for

¹⁸ Stocker, M., Darroch, L., Krahl, R., Habermann, T., Devaraju, A., Schwardmann, U., D'Onofrio, C. and Häggström, I., 2020. Persistent Identification of Instruments. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p.18. DOI: 10.5334/dsj-2020-018

¹⁹ Krahl, R., Darroch, L., Huber, R., Devaraju, A., Klump, J., Habermann, T., Stocker, M., & RDA PIDINST WG Members, (2022). Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments (1.0). DOI:

10.15497/RDA00070

²⁰ *Ibid.*

relatedIdentifierType are listed in Table 4. Most of these values have been adopted from the DataCite Metadata Schema²¹.

PDINST IDs, which are common to those identified by Heritage PIDs, are:

Value	Definition
ARK	Archival Resource Key: a URI designed to support long-term access to information objects.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier: a character string used to uniquely identify an object. A DOI name is divided into two parts a prefix and a suffix separated by a slash.

Extract from “Table 4: Values for relatedIdentifierType” (Krahl 2022)²²

Based on the data and practices collected from the case studies of the Heritage PIDs project and on the mandatory metadata defined by the RDA Persistent Identification of Instruments WG, it is possible to demonstrate that ARK and DOI are the most effective persistent and resolvable IDs in the internal and external identification of a CHO. This assumption does not rule out the use of internal IDs or non-resolvable IDs to identify a CHO.

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² *Ibid.*